

MECHANICAL ANALYSIS OF THERMOPLASTIC POLYMERS REINFORCED WITH ROBOTICALLY PLACED CONTINUOUS FIBER TOWS

P.-O. Hagstrand, N. Jansson, M. D. Wakeman, F. Bonjour and J.-A. E. Månson*

*Laboratoire de Technologie des Composites et Polymères (LTC)
Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL)
CH-1015 Lausanne, Switzerland*

ABSTRACT

A locally reinforced, generic structural part has experimentally and analytically been investigated. Test specimens were manufactured using an integrated processing technique where a UD fiber tow pre-impregnated with thermoplastic was robotically placed and subsequently over-molded to form a net-shape structure. The effect of fiber tow content and different placement speeds and pressures on the stiffness and strength of a glass fiber (gf) reinforced polypropylene (PP) composite was investigated by means of tensile tests. Moreover, simulations were performed to assess the predictive capabilities of both analytical and finite element models. Results include comparisons between the experimental and simulated tensile response of gf/PP specimens. Additionally, the analytical models were used to predict tensile properties of other multi-material combinations for comparison with possible rival materials, such as steel, aluminum and sheet molding compounds.

Key words: Thermoplastic composites, commingled fibers, tow placement, finite element method

INTRODUCTION

Manufacturing of multi-material composite structures using integrated processing is a novel manufacturing concept that offers the possibility of combining different materials in a optimal and cost effective way. The structural advantages of aligned, continuous fiber materials can be combined with the geometrical advantages offered by net shape flow based processes, such as injection and compression molding. By placing inserts of continuous fibers pre-impregnated with thermoplastic only in regions of higher operating load, structural performance can be achieved with a minimum amount of the more costly continuous fiber materials [1-2].

This process technology is currently being scaled up for high volume industrial applications. For successful industrial implementation, it is essential that short as well as long-term mechanical behavior are known and understood. Furthermore, it is important that mechanical properties can be predicted, both for materials selection purposes and for determination of optimum reinforcement content and placement location.

The work presented in this paper is part of a research scheme with the objective to generate knowledge and understanding of the mechanical behavior of structures manufactured by integrated processing. Within this work several aspects of the mechanical behavior, such as quasi-static, creep, damage and fatigue performance, are investigated. In this paper the tensile behavior of a generic structure, manufactured by integrated processing, is studied experimentally. The tensile behavior is also predicted by using both analytical and finite element modeling. Additionally, the analytical models are used to predict tensile properties of other alternative and commercially available multi-material combinations for comparison with possible rival materials, such as steel, aluminum and sheet molding compounds. Such a comparison can, especially when combined with cost modeling, be used to optimize this type of multi-material structure.

* To whom correspondence should be addressed

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials and Manufacturing

The generic multi-material structure consists of a robotically placed unidirectional (UD) commingled polypropylene/glass fiber tow loop, which is over-injection molded by short glass fiber reinforced polypropylene. The tow and the over-molding polymer contain 60 and 30 wt.% glass fibers, respectively. A CAD drawing of the structure (with the tow partly revealed) is shown in *Figure 1*. The generic structure has purposely been designed to enable the mechanical behavior, especially in tension, to be investigated. Molded-in metal bushings are used in order to enable realistic tensile loading with bolts. The over-molding polymer is injected from one of the short edges (see *Figure 1*). As a result, each coupon contains a weld line at the opposite short edge. Tow placement speed and the consolidation force were varied and in all four tow placement conditions were studied. The amount of tow was also varied from 0 to 36 vol.%. In total 8 different types of coupons were studied. A more detailed description of how the coupons were manufactured is given by Wakeman *et al.* [3].

Figure 1. CAD drawing of the studied generic multi-material structure with the continuous fiber loop partly revealed. The length of the structure is 300 mm.

Mechanical testing

The tensile behavior of the generic structure was studied by means of quasi-static tensile test. In previous tensile tests [3], the structure was loaded by 14 mm bolts through the steel bushings. As a result, the structure typically failed at the weld line (see *Figure 1*), and a failure load lower than expected was measured.

Figure 2. Coupon tested with the special grips that load the coupon simultaneously by bolts and profiled plates.

In an attempt to measure the intrinsic properties of the middle section, special fixtures were designed and manufactured. They enabled the load to be transferred to the structure simultaneously by 14 mm bolts through the bushings, and by profiled plates pressed against the sides by the bolts. In order to grip all samples in a consistent manner, the bolts were tightened with the same torque (13 Nm). Five coupons of each type were tested. A coupon loaded with these grips is shown in *Figure 2*.

All tensile tests were conducted using a MTS tensile machine with a 100 kN load cell. Strain was measured with a 135 mm gage-length extensometer. The tensile modulus was determined from the slope of the stress-strain curves in the strain interval 0.05% - 0.25% using MATLAB. The crosshead speed was 3 mm/min. All measurements were carried out at room temperature.

MODELING AND MATERIAL COMPARISON

Analytical modeling

The middle section of the studied generic structure is, from a modeling point of view, relatively simple. During tensile loading it can be assumed that the UD tow and the surrounding over molding polymer will be subjected to the same level of strain. Rule-of-mixtures based modeling can therefore be expected to predict the tensile behavior with good accuracy. The tensile elastic modulus, E and strength, σ_b as function of tow content were modeled using *Equations 1* and *2*, respectively.

$$E(V_{tow}) = E_{tow} \cdot V_{tow} + E_{matrix} \cdot (I - V_{tow}) \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_b(V_{tow}) = \sigma_{b,tow} \cdot V_{tow} + \sigma(\varepsilon_{b,tow})_{matrix} \cdot (I - V_{tow}) \quad (2)$$

where V_{tow} is the volume fraction of UD tow material in the middle section. The tow is expected to fail at a lower strain than the over molded polymer. $\sigma(\varepsilon_{b,tow})_{matrix}$ is therefore the estimated stress in the surrounding matrix at the strain level where the tow breaks. These equations were used for the material comparison, however, for the particular structure studied, the matrix was actually observed to break prior to tow failure. *Equation 3* and *4* were therefore used to predict the tensile properties in this case

$$\sigma_b(V_{tow}) = E_{tow} \cdot \varepsilon_{b,matrix} \cdot V_{tow} + \sigma_{b,matrix} \cdot (I - V_{tow}) \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma_b(V_{tow}) = \sigma_{b,tow} \cdot V_{tow} \quad (4)$$

where $\varepsilon_{b,matrix}$ is the measured strain to break of the matrix, $\sigma_{b,matrix}$ the measured strength of the matrix, and $\sigma_{b,tow}$ the strength of the tow material. Same type of modeling has previously been used to predict the tensile properties of glass mat thermoplastic (GMT) reinforced with a UD tow loop [4, 5].

Finite element modeling

As a complement to the analytical modeling, a finite element simulation of the experimental pin-pin setup with the specimen E4 was performed with ABAQUS, as shown in *Figure 3*. The material parameters used are given in *Table A4* in appendix. The tow is treated as a linear elastic, transversely isotropic material with the 1-direction as the fiber direction and the 2 and 3 directions in the plane of isotropy. The material properties not found elsewhere were estimated as: the transverse modulus by the Halpin-Tsai equation with $\xi = 2$, the compressive transverse fracture stress from the condition that the maximum shear stress should have reached its critical value, i.e.

$$\sigma_u^c = \sqrt{3}\tau_{23} \quad (5)$$

and the compressive fracture stress in the fiber direction from taking the failure strain equal to the failure strain of the tow containing 75 wt.% glass. As a failure criterion for the tow, the maximum stress criterion was used.

The material properties for elastic-plastic description of the matrix material were determined from the coupons without reinforcement (see later for experimental details). As the specimens without tow reinforcement did not break in the gage section, a finite element simulation was used to determine the critical maximum principal strain for the polymer matrix to be 2.5%. Due to symmetry, a quarter of the specimen was modeled with 67 000 tetrahedral elements while non-frictional contact was assumed between the specimen and the insert.

Figure 3. FE-model of a quarter of the E4 specimen with visible tow.

Material comparison

The analytical models described above were also used to predict mechanical properties of other alternative and commercially available multi-material combinations, such as PP, PA6, PA12 or PET reinforced with glass or carbon fiber tows. A summary of all analyzed material combinations is given in *Table 1*. Material data used for the analytical modeling are given in *Tables A1-A3* (Appendix).

Table 1. Analyzed multi-material combinations.

Multi-material code	TOW MATERIAL		OVER MOLDING POLYMER	
	Polymer	Fiber content	Polymer	Fiber content
PPGF60 + PPGF30	PP	60 wt.% glass	PP	30 wt.% glass
PPGF75 + PPGF30	PP	75 wt.% glass	PP	30 wt.% glass
PETGF65 + PETGF30	PET	65 wt.% glass	PET	30 wt.% glass
PPCF50 + PPGF30	PP	50 wt.% carbon	PP	30 wt.% glass
PA6CF60 + PA6GF30	PA6	60 wt.% carbon	PA6	30 wt.% glass
PA12CF69 + PA12GF30	PA12	69 wt.% carbon	PA12	30 wt.% glass

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Experimental tensile properties

The effect of tow placement conditions on tensile properties is summarized in *Table 2*. As can be seen, the various tow placement conditions have no distinct effect on the tensile modulus and strength, even though the strain at maximum stress of the C4 and D4 coupons appears to be higher than for the A4 and B4 coupons. On the other hand, strain data close to failure must be treated with caution since non-fatal crack opening within the extensometer gage length may cause erroneous strain measurement readings.

Table 2. Effect of tow placement conditions on tensile properties.

	A4	B4	C4	D4

Tow content [vol.%]	18	18	18	18
Tow placement speed [mm/s]	20	20	100	100
Consolidation force [N]	20	80	20	80
Tensile modulus [GPa]	9.84 ± 0.39	9.68 ± 0.41	9.68 ± 0.50	10.10 ± 0.38
Tensile strength [MPa]	124.0 ± 2.4	125.0 ± 6.1	124.6 ± 9.0	122.5 ± 3.7
Strain at maximum stress [%]	1.7 ± 0.11	1.7 ± 0.16	2.3 ± 0.77	2.3 ± 1.0

That the different placement conditions have no significant effect on the tensile properties is not surprising. Consolidation forces and placement speed will mainly affect the void content within the tow. However, during tensile loading of the particular glass/polypropylene tow, about 95% of the load will be carried by the glass fibers. Thus, as long as the load can be transferred efficiently to the glass fibers, voids in the surrounding polypropylene should have only a limited effect on tensile performance. Bending properties on the other hand will probably be affected to a larger extent.

In *Table 3* the effect of tow content on tensile properties is summarized. The injection molding parameters of the E coupons are slightly different compared to the A-D coupons. The E0 coupons consist of just the PPGF30 material. Compared to the material data given by the supplier (see *Table A1*), these coupons exhibit considerably lower strength and strain to break. This is probably due to different fiber orientation and processing conditions. Additionally, the stress concentrations generated by the geometry itself and the loading grips decrease the apparent strength. For the other coupons, it is clear that the tensile modulus and strength increase with increasing tow content.

Table 3. Effect of tow content on tensile properties.

	E0	E4	E6	E8
Tow content [vol.%]	0	18	27	36
Tow placement speed [mm/s]	100	100	100	100
Consolidation force [N]	80	80	80	80
Tensile modulus [GPa]	6.28 ± 0.25	9.81 ± 0.21	11.55 ± 0.33	13.72 ± 0.47
Tensile strength [MPa]	75.6 ± 2.1	140.1 ± 3.2	186.2 ± 13.9	228.4 ± 21.9
Strain at maximum stress [%]	2.1 ± 0.1	1.9 ± 0.14	2.0 ± 0.24	2.0 ± 0.2

The special grips were found to promote failure in the middle section, although a few samples failed close to the grips where the coupon thickness changes. This is not surprising since the coupon to some extent is loaded there and the thickness reduction generates a stress concentration. Cracking at the weld line was observed in a few cases for E6 and E8 coupons. However, these coupons still failed primarily in the middle section or at the thickness reduction. Thus, weld line failure was never observed to be the dominating failure mode.

Predicted tensile properties

For comparison with predicted tensile properties from the modeling, tow content in the various coupons is required. E4 coupons for example, contain 4 turns of tow (where the tow itself contains 5 yarns). Since the weight/meter and the density of the consolidated yarn are known, tow content can be calculated (see *Tables 2* and *3*).

In *Figures 4* and *5*, measured and predicted tensile properties are compared. The upper modeling results (in red) are based on ideal matrix properties (see *Table A1*), whereas, the lower are based on measured matrix properties. As can be seen, the analytical model predicts the stiffness of the structure with reasonable accuracy, especially when the measured matrix modulus is used for modeling. The tensile strength, however, is clearly more difficult to predict. This is not surprising since the model is based on the assumptions that all fibers are perfectly straight and aligned, and that there are no voids in the materials. Furthermore, in contrast to the FE model, the analytical model is unable to take

geometrical effects into account. Nevertheless, analytical modeling can be useful for the prediction of stiffness and to roughly estimate the strength of the structure.

Figure 4. Predicted tensile modulus compared with experimental results.

Figure 5. Predicted tensile strength compared with experimental results.

Finite element results for the E4 specimen

No attempt was made to include the modified grips in the modeling of the E4 specimen; instead it was assumed that the load was introduced in a way that prevented failure in the grip area while the stress distribution outside the gripping area was not significantly altered. In *Figure 6*, the force versus strain response from the simulation is compared with the experimental results; the last point on the simulation curve corresponds to the predicted fatal failure load. In the current analysis, final failure is considered to occur when either the maximum tow stress in the fiber-direction is attained or the critical matrix strain is reached. A non-catastrophic failure is predicted to occur due to transverse failure of the tow at a load of approximately 26 kN. No attempt was made to include the effect of this in the analysis. Final failure is then predicted to be due to matrix failure at a load of ~41 kN and a strain of ~1.7%.

Figure 6. Force versus strain for the simulation of the E4 specimen compared to the experimental results.

Material comparison

To model analytically is a time efficient way to estimate tensile properties of potential material combinations with different tow content. Such a comparison can, especially when combined with cost modeling, be used for material selection purposes and to optimize the composition.

Figure 7. Tensile modulus as a function of volume fraction of UD tow in the structure. Carbon fiber based structures exhibit, as expected, a superior tensile modulus compared to glass fiber based structures.

Figure 8. Tensile strength as a function of volume fraction of UD tow in the

Figure 9. Specific tensile modulus as a function of volume fraction of UD tow in the structure. Glass fiber based structures cannot compete with steel or aluminium. Carbon fiber based structures on the other hand, exhibit a very high specific tensile modulus.

In *Figure 7*, tensile modulus as a function of volume fraction of UD tow is shown. Glass fiber based systems have, as can be seen, relatively low modulus and can only compete with other low modulus materials such as sheet molding compounds. Carbon fiber based systems on the other hand exhibit considerably higher stiffness and can compete with aluminum. The tensile strength as a function of volume fraction of UD tow is shown in *Figure 8*. This suggests that even glass fiber based systems have relatively high strength and can compete with both steel and aluminum.

In order to estimate the weight saving potential of the different materials, one must take into account the density by, for example, comparing the specific properties. In *Figure 9* the specific tensile modulus as a function of UD tow content is shown. Still it is clear that the specific tensile stiffness of steel or aluminum cannot be matched with glass fiber based composites. However, carbon fiber based systems exhibit, as expected, very high specific modulus, and can compete with metals even with relatively low tow content levels around 20-30 vol.%. *Figure 10* shows the specific strength as a function of UD tow content. Clearly, the specific tensile strength of glass and carbon fiber based structures is superior to that of steel, aluminum and structural SMC.

From the results presented above it is clear that replacement of steel or aluminum with glass fiber based system can generate weight savings, however mainly for applications where the structural strength is the most important design criteria. Carbon fiber based systems on the other hand, can generate weight savings even for applications where the stiffness is the main design criteria.

CONCLUSIONS

A thermoplastic, tow reinforced structure has been manufactured by robotic tow placement followed by over-injection molding. Specimens with different tow placement speeds and pressures were made and subsequently tested in tension. No influence of the placement conditions on tensile properties could be observed. The experimental results were also compared with predictions from both analytical and numerical methods to determine the applicability of the models. The comparisons indicate that the analytical modeling is useful for the prediction of stiffness and to estimate the strength of the structure. FE simulations on the other hand give for the current case, an excellent prediction of the strength as well as the stiffness. Finally, the analytical model was applied to compare the properties of tow reinforced thermoplastics to competing materials; the main conclusions were that carbon tows were necessary to obtain specific stiffness properties as high as metals whereas the specific strength of glass fiber tow materials can compete with that of metals.

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APPENDIX

Material data used for analytical modeling

Table A1. Material data of the short glass fiber reinforced thermoplastics matrices.

	PPGF30	PETGF30	PA6GF30	PA12GF30
Tensile modulus [GPa]	7.4	10.7	5.7	6.0
Tensile strength [MPa]	104	159	110	115
Strain to break [%]	3.5	2.7	<7	6
Density [g/cm³]	1.14	1.56	1.36	1.22

Table A2. Material data of the UD tow materials.

	PPGF60	PPGF75	PETGF65	PPCF50	PA6CF60	PA12CF69
Tensile modulus [GPa]	28	38	37.6	78	112	129
Tensile strength [MPa]	700	800	870	1275	1850	2130
Strain to break [%]	-	-	-	1.64	1.64	1.64
Density [g/cm³]	1.47	1.75	1.9	1.2	1.45	1.45

Table A3. Used material data of possible rival materials.

	Steel	Aluminum	SMC R-50
Tensile modulus [GPa]	210	70	15
Tensile strength [MPa]	400	225	160
Density [g/cm³]	7.8	2.7	2.0

Material data used for finite element modeling

Table A4. Material properties of the tow material used for the FE-modeling.

E_{11}	$E_{22} = E_{33}$	$G_{12} = G_{13}$	G_{23}	$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$	ν_{23}
28 GPa	4.4 GPa	1.39 GPa	1.36 GPa	0.4	0.62
σ_{11}	$\sigma_{22} = \sigma_{33}$	$\tau_{12} = \tau_{13}$	τ_{23}	σ_{11}^C	$\sigma_{22}^C = \sigma_{33}^C$
700 MPa	7.6 MPa	19 MPa	12 MPa	121 MPa	21 MPa